

How can *you* contribute to the social responsibility of your university's education?

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In this SEFI ethics SIG-workshop, we actively engage with the question: “How can *you* contribute to the social responsibility of your university's education?”

This is an important question for university staff.

First, universities become (and see themselves) as increasingly important players to contribute to the sustainable development goals. Their missions [1]–[3] and strategies [4] broaden to more research, entrepreneurship and social responsibility. From the perspective of being recognized as important actors in the quintuple helix of innovation [5], (technical) university eco-system collaborations become increasingly co-creative, including complex interactions between political, economic, and education systems, natural environment and knowledge creation [6]. The technical universities' education also becomes increasingly intertwined with the eco-system partners, resulting in adapting curricula [7] and new and flexible [8] formats for ethics courses [9] such as research-based, community-based or challenge-based learning.

Second, in this transition, teachers change inevitably from purely internal staff to societal actors [10]. Willingly or unwillingly, you as an individual teacher get a more pronounced societal role, as an agent of social change (e.g. [11]). This means a growing realization that, in the language of Paulo Freire, “Education is politics...when a teacher realizes that he or she is a politician too, the teacher has to ask, What kind of politics am I doing in the classroom? That is, in favor of whom am I being a teacher?” [3:46].

If we approach this from the responsibility angle, Whitbeck's definition “exercise of judgment and care to achieve or maintain a desirable state of affairs” [4:159] can be a starting point here. As Fore and Hess note while introducing their five-sided framework of ethical becoming, “rules and codes found in discipline-specific standards are undoubtedly important, [but] insufficient by themselves for moral inquiry and ethical judgement” [5:1355]. The reflection of the impact of education to the university's responsibility then requires a focus on the actual context and social practices [15] and a broader perspective on all involved (students, teachers, university, eco-system) [16].

For the session, we propose the following **agenda**:

1. Short introduction of the context of the workshop
2. Break-out groups
 - What is your role in the university? (Ethics) teacher? (Educational) manager? What do you care about”? What do you want to change or influence? Do you focus on the classroom activities? Or do you reflect on how your activities (teaching, research, ...) have a broader impact?

How do you judge things as a desirable state of affairs? How does ethics come into play?

What can you “exercise”? What can you do? What is your agency or influence? How is it limited (university, other contexts)? Do you want more influence?

- Who can or should you involve in co-constructing the educational agenda and reaching educational goals?
 - How do you evaluate your influence? Student satisfaction or student learning? Do you also use input from other partners?
3. Plenum discussion, in which we bring together the different inputs and have an overall discussion.

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